

SYNERWEEE Code documentation

Version 1.0

Synthetic Data for Enhanced Refurbishment
of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment

Project acronym: SYNERWEEE

Release date: 15 September 2025

Version: v1.0

Primary repository: <https://github.com/Clearbox-AI/SYNERWEEE>

1 . Introduction

The SYNERWEE project addresses the pervasive issue of data scarcity when training machine learning algorithms for the recycling of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), specifically laptops.

In industrial settings, obtaining sufficient real-world data for tasks like laptop refurbishment is challenging, time-consuming, and expensive due to the manual effort required for data collection and annotation.

We propose a method to generate synthetic images of laptops with surface defects to enhance the datasets used to train detection models for the identification of damaged laptops and improve their performance.

This project is based on the work presented in the paper [Diffusion-based Image Generation for In-distribution Data Augmentation in Surface Defect Detection](#).

The code is available at <https://github.com/Clearbox-AI/SYNERWEEE>. (currently available for project consortium partners. It will be available for public at the end of the project in March 2026.)

2. Instructions for repository & environment setup

1. Set up the repository:

```
$ git clone https://github.com/Clearbox-AI/SYNERWEEE.git
```

2. Set up the environment:

```
- $ conda create -n in_and_out python=3.10
- $ conda activate in_and_out
- $ pip install torch==1.12.0+cu113 torchvision==0.13.0+cu113
torchaudio==0.12.0 --extra-index-url
https://download.pytorch.org/whl/cu113
- $ cd sd_utilities/
- $ pip install --upgrade -r requirements.txt
- $ pip install xformers==0.0.20
- $ pip install bitsandbytes==0.38.1
- $ accelerate config
```

3. Download the Stable Diffusion model:

```
- sd-v1-5-pruned-noema-fp16.safetensors
```

And store it within `/sd_utilities/models/`.

3. Image generation with Stable Diffusion and fine tuning

Firstly, enter inside the `sd_utilities/` folder with the command:

```
$ cd sd_utilities/
```

Make sure the `.sh` files are executable by running:

```
$ chmod +x sd_utilities/*.sh
```

Then:

1. To generate new images from the pretrain of SD, use the script `3_launch_generate_imgs.sh`. In particular:

Use the parameter `--ckpt` to specify the path of the SD model, set as default `models/sd-v1-5-pruned-noema-fp16.safetensors`.

2. To finetune the pretrain of SD:

- For each image in the dataset, create the corresponding label using the script `utils/generate_lbls.py`.

- The token that you specify must have the form `sks type_of_item`.

- Specifically, your dataset folder should then have the following structure:

```
Dataset_folder
|-- img001.png
|-- img001.txt
|-- img002.png
|-- img002.txt
|-- img00N.png
|-- img00N.txt
```

- Since we use the Deamooth technique, we need to generate at least 200 regularization images. In order to do this:

- Generate 200 new images through the script `3_launch_generate_imgs.sh`, using the token `type_of_item`.

- Generate the corresponding labels using the script `utils/generate_lbls.py` and the token `type_of_item`.

- Put in the same folder your own images (and labels) and the regularization images (and labels)

- Use the file `1_launch_finertuning.sh` to finetune the SD model

- Check that all the parameters in `dataset_config.toml` are correct

- Since we are also using the LoRA technique, use the file `2_launch_merge_lora.sh` to merge the weights

- Use the file `3_launch_generate_imgs.sh` with the prompt `sks type_of_item` to generate the new images

- Use the parameter `--ckpt` to specify the path of the finetuned SDLoRA model

3.1 Computational resources

The fine-tuning of the model was performed on a machine equipped with two Nvidia T4 GPUs of 16 GB each.

4. Results (Early results, September 2025)

The results from the first fine-tuning are promising, delivering accurate images with realistic surface defects.

Below are some examples of training (Figure 1) and generated (Figure 2) images.

Figure 1 - Example of real training images.

Figure 2 - Example of images generated with fine-tuned SDXL.

Contacts

info@clearbox.ai

<https://clearbox.ai>

This project is developed in the framework of the **euROBIN** consortium.

Funded by the European Union